

The Ergonomic Holistic Management Strategy against the Covid-19 Pandemic

Tjokorda Bagus Putra Marhaendra¹, Yeyen Komalasari², I Gusti Bagus Rai Utama³

^{1,2,3}Management of Dhyana Pura University, Bali, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: Ergonomics or Human Factors are natural laws of human activities that involve physicals and mental (spirituality). As an applied science, ergonomics is multidisciplinary and interdisciplinary with other sciences. Therefore, to solve human problems, ergonomics uses other science. Such as strategic management, which in the business benefits the economy and the environment sustainably. However, environmental damage by human activity causes the Coronavirus out of its origins and establishes humans as their new host. When COVID-19 spread globally and caused many casualties, the pandemic occurred. After more than one year, it seems humans have not yet learned from the pandemic. Whereas, the public behaviour and selfishly against pandemic caused blundering solutions of the government and experts. Even applying synthetic herd immunity needs years. Observing these situations and conditions required an ergonomic holistic approach. The goal of a holistic strategy is to solve the problem from various aspects. It leads to the public-awareness response of critical conditions and situations. Therefore, self-leadership must be intensified to safety the self, family, and society by raising the body's immunity. Besides mass vaccination, it would be nice if immunity was formed naturally by food and a healthy lifestyle, and practicing Yoga. For that reason, people should return to the old values and use natural resources for life.

KEYWORDS: Ergonomics, Strategic Management, Synthetic Herd Immunity, Self-Awareness.

INTRODUCTION

Recently, the handling against the pandemic has been increasingly intense in line with national, regional, and global economic recovery efforts. Indeed, handling the pandemic and economic recovery are not options that are to be determined separately. Although, it is not easy to maintain both at once. Several countries are concentrating on against pandemics by spending a lot of money. The other implement an open-close system to counter the pandemic while providing opportunities for economic growth, no matter how small it is. However, after more than a year, the various methods have not yielded significant results. The pandemic is spreading intensively, and economic growth is declining.

Based on those backgrounds, this study proposed solutions to solve pandemic and economic problems. Considering both are not separate issues, they require a comprehensive analysis of human activity and social behavior. At this level, the holistic approach involves various research in pandemics, ergonomics, and strategic management.

Ergonomics or Human Factors are not merely about physical activities for work only. Although the International Ergonomics Association (IEA) interchangeably both as one unit, it is not only physical activities. Since humans consist of the physical and mental (spirituality) are inseparable. IEA Council deciding determined ergonomics as: "Ergonomics (or human factors) is the scientific discipline concerned with the understanding of interactions among humans and other elements of a system, and the profession that applies theory, principles, data, and methods to design to optimize human well-being and overall system performance" (IEA, n.d.).

Therefore, ergonomics is 'the structured plan of action in optimizing human activity to achieve human well-being.' It is applied science that involves other sciences. Even though they are multidisciplinary and interdisciplinary, they do not overlap, but they reinforce from one to another. Its goals are to solve achievements which are problem-solving, alternative solutions, making more productive, making comfortable, promoting health, and not merely economic benefits. Finally, every science involved continues to evolve. Therefore, ergonomics uses some parts of the other science, and *vice versa*, such as strategic management uses to solve the problems; that dealing by humans-being in their work and other activities.

Strategic management is a part of management science proposed from the art of war. Strategic planning began in military activity (David and David, 2017). Concurrently, ergonomics science introduced by Hywel Murrell at the end of World War two in England (Pheasant and Haslegrave, 2015). And strategic management does not merely support related sciences for increased human performance in their organization to attaining its objectives. Therefore, both are effective head-to-head to face critical situations and conditions to resolve human problems.

However, human behavior involves many aspects that influence work attitudes and other activities. One of them represents the mental (spirituality) aspect. Spirituality is the value that reflects on traditional life in its culture (see in Marhaendra, 2016). When ergonomics explores humans, as human well-being; it is additionally a concern of psychosocial and sociopsychological. For instance, currently, another branch of ergonomics development is *neuroergonomics* (Johnson & Proctor, 2013), which is exceedingly close to medical science, neuroscience. It intended to understand human behavior in work attitude and other activities, from the physiologic of psychological related to activities of the brain.

OVERVIEW OF HOW DISEASE BECAME PANDEMICS

At the end of 2019, after the events of The Black Death (Aberth, 2005) centuries ago, humans are back against the pandemic. Compared to the science, technology, health capabilities, and quality of life today, this event seems worse than The Black Death. Pandemics do not merely happen, in the beginning, followed by some symptoms, then spread throughout the world. The problem is, modern people are exceptionally busy taking care of themselves. In modernity, human support by advanced transportation and information technology. They are very active traveling around the world in minutes or hours. Unfortunately, on the way, there is something unnoticed attaching them, and it's untraced by sensor devices. Therefore, they overlook the slight signs or symptoms or might underestimate them. In the beginning, that overlook symptoms, as reported by WHO (2020a), in Wuhan City, Hubei Province, China, has detected the group of pneumonia caused by an unknown etiology (unknown cause). It subsequently spreads to the world within a few months, and it increases locally in a count of weeks or days. Even though, people receive frequent information about it online every second.

What has happened in Wuhan City might be one of many examples impact of environmental changes. However, people express diverse perspectives on environmental sustainability. Because in some points of public views, corporate benefits take from the people and their environment. Therefore, preserving the environment remains the responsibility of the corporate. Although preserved environmental sustainability attends are everyone's duty. However, when a human's activities (people and or in the name of corporate) damages the environment, then nature balances itself in its way. And of its activity presentation, humans react and see it as a disaster.

The lack of self-awareness, besides ignorance, mostly misleading pandemic information, hoaxes. And such conspiracy theories are viral among people. It occurs because of obstruction of the transparency of communication and information. As a consequence, people seek out by themselves and connect various phenomena with complex logic that are simplified. This misleading information is undoubtedly and confusing, even for thoroughly intellectual people. In the intervening period, the public was waiting for certainty in confusion by the crowd information. Along with it, the victims of the pandemic began falling and spread everywhere.

Why take accordingly long to decide against the pandemic? Begin with the term of the pandemic, Yamamoto states that, "The origin of the word lies in Greek, in which *pan* means 'all' and *dēmos* mean 'people.' ... It now refers to an infectious disease that spreads globally and causes mortality on a significant scale" (Yamamoto, 2013). And now, referring to the term 'significant scale,' how much causality matching in it? Suppose it is a match, then how to prevent the spreading? The government, when determining policy, causes two implications. First, the readiness of the government itself, and second the social reactions to it. And what happens in many countries? Both are difficult to obtain general ground. It is related to the social trust in its government. Therefore, without it, the strategic plan against the pandemic being critical to apply in public.

When observing the background events, this is the impact of environmental destruction by people's activity that modifies the behavior of the living-being those live in it. And it caused the living being to leave its origins, and one of these kinds established humans as its current hosts. This tiny living being, its size in the micron and imperceptible for ordinary eyes, has been identified by experts and named Coronavirus (COVID-19). Then spread around the world, infecting people who retained nothing to effect with its living before. Naturally, people try surviving as well as COVID-19, and it is a habitual behavior. Since the human effort to make it, Coronavirus reacts more adaptive than before, like regenerating and mutating themselves with many variants. The evidence was

received by WHO from national authorities as of 31 January 2021. Variants of COVID-19, four types reported, have spread around the world (WHO, 2021a). Furthermore, many reports from national authorities around the world state there are more variants of COVID-19.

RESEARCH METHODS

The study focus on the library is used as a desk research method by online techniques for searching information to collect data from official sources of WHO (World Health Organization), scientific publications sources, and other secondary sources. And analysis technique used is a descriptive qualitative, analogy, and simulation made according to some research results and other scientific publications related to solved human problems against pandemics. And ergonomic holistic and strategic management as the lead manages the research sources to obtain a clear and constructive analysis.

ERGONOMIC HOLISTIC AND STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT

The difficulty in overcoming human problems is when involving various aspects. Therefore, ergonomic holistic has integrated multidisciplinary and interdisciplinary sciences to solve human problems, as human-being in their work and other activities. Salvendy summarized the proposals from ergonomics experts; states: the ergonomics discipline promotes a holistic, human-centered approach to work systems design that considers the physical, cognitive, social, organizational, environmental, and other relevant factors (Salvendy, 2012). With this description, people can recognize a holistic approach in an ergonomics context.

As stated by Diamond, understanding is more often used to try to alter an outcome than to reiterate or perpetuate it (Diamond, 1999). That is why scientists (researchers) do not attempt to justify or unjustified what happened. Alternatively, they tried to use their understanding of the causal chain to break or interrupt the chain. Therefore, there is a space of possibility to resolve it. The same applies to ergonomics; it is not only interrupting but seeks to overcome problems with holistic approaches. Manuaba (2007) proposes an approach using the term SHIP, which consists of Systemic, Holistic, Interdisciplinary, and Participatory, known as total ergonomics. This approach can merge into one word, holistic, *vice versa* mean of the total. It is ergonomics represent ergonomics holistically. The human problems are related to physical and mental (spirituality) conditions that impact behavior and attitudes. For the case, the 'tools' utilized to solve the problem, based on a holistic study, indeed are finite in the ideas as an alternative solution. And for all actions initiated from the idea of the academic perspective that direction to solve the problems. The issue is whether people are willing to put that idea into the ergonomic action or not.

Ergonomics action is how humans work and other activities naturally, without coercion, reducing unnecessary burdens both physically and mentally (spirituality), but still productive. And acknowledging the limitations of human beings. The key to productivity is "Work Smart, Not to Work Hard" (Konz and Johnson, 2016). However, human activities are not merely "Work" (2020) in physics. Interaction with work organization; work tools; workplace; and work environment. Suppose activity is affirmative to work activities (work and work), even 'smart' related to mental aspects. At that point, ergonomics will stop when many works doing by robots and artificial humans (humanoid). It is possible since artificial intelligence unnecessarily needs natural rules of work, job risks are all born by the machine. Which may have small fault tolerance, and the solution approach is different from humans. Therefore, back to the understanding of work. According to Oxford Dictionary, work is being engaged in a physical or mental activity to achieve a result ("Work," n.d.). Even though productivity, not only an economic perspective, but activities that intensify health are equally productive. Now people realize that life is not merely seeking job satisfaction. However, also life from welfare to well-being. Although to compensate for its limitations, people are using technology and its system, but still under control by people. Therefore, people must be enlightened in technology and not exploited by technology. Besides knowledge, competency, and ability in technology, it requires self-leadership.

Self-leadership that inspires by Gandhi's thinking about being independent of the self as a part of the family and society. There are two fundamentals of Gandhi conveyed were *Swaraj* and *Swadeshi* (Kaur and Singh, 2015). The term of *Swaraj* in general meaning is self-rule, and in the most limited scopes represent self-leadership; it exceeds people to act unselfishly and without violence. While the term *Swadeshi* attends to people's effort independently use the present resources for their life. And build an economy for its family and community with fundamental technology and environmentally friendly. Therefore, for today's life, this is an intelligible principle. Freed from the exploits of human-being, and promoted self-reliance with self-discovery and self-learning; in meeting the needs of life from nature and work with its proper technology. It is the fundamental principle of ergonomic behavior

and attitude; to 'optimize human well-being,' there is the human's central point of view in 'Human Factors' (IEA, n.d.). After all, this is not far away from ergonomics, which is from the Greek words: Ergon - work; Nomos - natural law (CU Ergo, n.d.).

Meanwhile, strategic management represents: the art and science of formulating, implementing, and evaluating cross-functional decisions that enable an organization to achieve its objectives (David and David, 2017). Which is to accomplish its goals, and every science has utilized the construct process of plan action in work organization. It consists of three stages of strategy, and in every step of its, each science included reviews the character as the specialty of its knowledge, competency, and ability. The three stages of strategy are formulation, implementation, and evaluation (David and David, 2017).

Suppose strategic management with its three stages applies to the business. Ultimately lead to a competitive advantage. The firm obtains a competitive advantage; when it can generate more economic value than rival firms (Barney and Hesterly, 2015). Although to gain benefits more than its competitors, it should not just play by its own rules. It is the same as racing cars on municipal roads; the racer must respect others and awareness of the situation and condition of the road. Therefore, each corporation must have a social responsibility and environmental sustainability. There is a difference between sustainability and sustainable development (Thatcher and Yeow, 2018). Which strategy is adopted to obtain economic benefits with social and environmental responsibility equally? Perhaps, the winner abandoned the defeated, and the responsibility of the remnants is on the defeated side. It is the result of competition when competition is the same as the enemy in a war. Therefore, corporates and stakeholders should be understood psychosociology, environmental ethics and design the work ergonomically. And still maintained competitiveness in its quality of products, services, and position in the market segmentation. Subsequently, to achieve an improved equality role; then the policy for collaboration and partnership models become an innovative approach. The goal, hopefully, is the benefit in economics is just as good as in environmental sustainability. However, the expectations from the innovative approach turned out to be fruitless yet. The world is nonetheless in the environmental breakdown and raised extreme climate change.

SIMULATION SYNTHETIC HERD IMMUNITY AGAINST PANDEMIC

There is hope, and the name is herd immunity. However, that hope also causes debate for some reason. It said that natural herd immunity is unethical and inhuman because people be barely hopeless and death. Otherwise, WHO supports achieving 'herd immunity' through vaccination, not by allowing the disease to spread through any segment of populations, as this would result in unnecessary cases and deaths (WHO, 2020b). Therefore, the term of herd immunity has to be distinguished the natural and synthetic (artificial). It is significant to reaffirm that herd immunity by allowing immunity that occurs naturally in the community is natural herd immunity. Meanwhile, herd immunity through mass vaccination to the community is synthetic herd immunity.

Traditionally, such as in ancient times, herd immunity represents a natural selection. When a plague hits an area, people only try to survive as much as could until the plague disappears by itself. The diseases are not disappearing. However, those who are still alive during that plague have produced antibodies against and defeat the disease. There is a terrible battle. Even though, The Black Death states that all point to death rates between 40% to 70% (Aberth, 2005). Therefore, as founded by D'souza and Dowdy, "When most of a population is immune to an infectious disease, this provides indirect protection - or herd immunity (also called herd protection) - to those who are not immune to the disease" (D'souza and Dowdy, 2020). And they point out by an example: "If 80% of a population is immune to a virus, four out of every five people who encounter someone with the disease won't get sick (and won't spread the disease any further). In this way, the spread of infectious diseases is keeping under control (D'souza and Dowdy, 2020). And they also argue the ranges of the population to achieve herd immunity, "... usually, 50% to 90% of a population needs immunity to achieve herd immunity" (D'souza and Dowdy, 2020). The meaning is when The Black Death occurred, people that acquired no immunity are higher than the immune people; that is why many died during the plague. Cause by various factors, including lack of community health due to poverty. Therefore, against viruses or other diseases, the key is the body's immunity.

However, in terms of the threshold, the proportional population percentage to achieve herd immunity through mass vaccination against the COVID-19 not ascertain yet. Research on immunity to the COVID-19 is in the study. WHO states, "Until we better understand COVID-19 immunity, it will not be possible to know how much of a population is immune and how long that immunity lasts, for let alone makes future predictions" (WHO, 2020b). Calculation of the proportions to meet the threshold is depending on many factors. Among others: demographics compositions; prioritize rank according to the spreading; efficacy of the vaccine, and other (unexpected) factors.

The purpose of this simulation is to acknowledge the difficulty of mass vaccination. The threshold is setting for the world's population. Suppose estimation the world population at 50% - 90% (D'souza and Dowdy, 2020), and taken in the middle, it will represent 70% of the world's population. Estimate the world population in 2020 at 7.8 billion people (UNFPA, n.d.); then there have to be 5.46 billion vaccines available. Furthermore, how many factories can produce the vaccine, and how long produce the vaccine that much? According to data at the document "Status of COVID-19 Vaccines within WHO EUL/PQ Evaluation Process," which was released on 01 February 2021. It is 15 manufacturers in the world that produce COVID-19 Vaccines (WHO, n.d.). It means each factory produced vaccine an average of 364 million. Suppose each manufacture of affordable produce vaccine at one million every day. Then it took almost one year to complete the product. It not including the problem in maintaining the conditions of the vaccine during the journey to its destination. Therefore, in calculations on paper, it might take more than two years to conduct this treatment. Meanwhile, the spread and mutation of COVID-19 escalated and expanded, and it's should raise new problems in vaccine efficacy.

Eventually, the problem above proved by WHO in its press release states, "Of the 128 million vaccine doses administered so far, more than three-quarters of those vaccinations are in just ten countries that account 60% of global GDP (WHO, 2021b). And on the other side, WHO mentions, "... almost 130 countries, with 2.5 billion people, are yet to administer a single dose (WHO, 2021b). Indeed, this situation looks like a ping-pong game effect. Therefore, "This self-defeating strategy will cost lives and livelihoods, give the virus further opportunity to mutate and evade vaccines, and will undermine a global economic recovery" (WHO, 2021b).

FINDING

More than one year against the pandemic, but in several countries still spread locally, then the second wave has come, even though in several country has faced the third wave. Simultaneously, the other countries found a more recent variant of Coronavirus. According to WHO in its release, for the first time, four of the various variants of COVID-19 have spread around the world. The first administer of the anti-virus vaccine started around February - March 2021 (WHO, 2021b), although nonconforming the threshold yet. And two weeks after the second vaccine, the spread of COVID-19 is still high. The health protocols tightened to the community in social activities and sanctions for violators. However, the situation and condition still are not better yet.

Effect on personal

There are at least two possible basics that lead to slowing down the recovery process. The first reason endures bodily conditions. It is related to the economic decline and the uncertainty of when a pandemic end. Therefore, they prepare to survive in the long term. Especially for those who, for some reason, are no longer working. They live on limited sources of income. Even though there are restrictions on their activities by working and studying from home, they keep trying to live provided. While, the other needs are increasing, like electricity bills, freshwater, telephone, and the internet. Hence, they eat in moderation, and this affects their nutritional intake. And second reason represents the mental (spirituality) condition. How do modern humans possibly survive in an almost monotonous state for months? Although not as extreme as imagined. They feel imprisoned in their own home. It is hard to apply the health protocols with restrictions on social activities as they live every day. This situation certainly has an impact on undermining of mental (spirituality). The typical symptoms are decreasing appetite, stress, depression, emotional disturbance, and some might even be worse. Ultimately, in a long time, not everyone could adapt to its life changes. Those represent the two possibilities of conditions above; that could have an impact on individual immunity. Although the effect on the body depends on someone's health, it varies from person to person. However, there is the interaction between the physical and mental (spirituality) are influence each other.

Effect on social behavior

The government and experts have been an effort strategically to established against COVID-19. The components used to solve the problems are already available. The formulation and methods already have, and the implementation has been going on. And every specialist is supported by the proper tools and devices they need. However, after more than one year has passed, why encounter the problem been unresolved yet? There something goes wrong; when closer inspection it turns out the problem is substantially from social behavior. This problem obtains the causal effects, predominantly followed by the people. Social behavior reflects how each person reacts to critical conditions and situations. It also shows the awareness level of the people until the direct event impacts them.

When observing various reports of the COVID-19; and how the people commonly reacted to be aware of the potential harms; and how they reacted to the pandemic. Founded when the threat is still potentially, then any form of warning be ignored. Otherwise, after the potential transformed into a concrete event, people became excessive, panic. At that time, notifications in any form will violate. And people are not even learning from what happens to them. It seems this behavior is constantly replicated, even in altered cases.

For example, there is a fascinating case. It happens in the community when there is an announcement of the increase in fuel prices set on a particular date. The day before notification took effect, there were long queues at each fuel station. Traffic jams occur everywhere. The behavior patterns change slowly after a few times of the same notification. Furthermore, such notice seemed to cause no significant effect. However, after that, many complained when the prices of goods and necessities of life increased.

It means most people are slow to discover the causal correlation between an increase in fuel prices and increase in production costs and their availability in the market. Not only to meet the needs at that time, indeed, but they are also willing to queue at the fuel station for hours on the road and cause traffic jams. The notices intend that preceded increase in fuel prices were prompt to the people, which is to be prepared to withstand the impact of the increased payment. In this manner, they are capable of managing daily living expenses.

It is also happening in the news, primarily following the principle: “good news is bad news.” What has frequently described the news? “When somebody bites by the dog, it is not news. However, when someone bites the dog, that is news.” In this way, news developed how people perceive the information. Especially accompanied by the unstoppable advancement of information technology and user-friendly social media, ordinary people also can make their stories and news. At that point, the problem emerged from the witch’s lack of journalistic ethics and its law. Many became victims of news coverage, also judicial cases related to reporting. Ultimately, people are easily unconvinced by the news. It appears merely entertainment, although not all news is bad news. People know the accuracy of the news; they did by comparing with the similar news from the official’s news; or the other mainframe media that they trusted because of its reputation. In general, after they obtain the first information from other media.

An example of good news is bad news. When the pandemic was raging, the government enforced the community for health protocols with various social restrictions and suggested staying at home. While at home, each family is assisted with primary needs by the government, but there is an inequitable distribution due to several problems, like population data. The data problem had occurred before the pandemic. It was unresolved by officers with those people involved yet. They unrealize that the effectiveness of distribution and accountability of assisting depends on the accuracy of the data. Indeed, this incident captured headlines in the mass media. Did they learn from this incident? Perhaps both forgot the matter, and people were disappointed when the aids unreached them yet. And the fundamental question has to answer; what should be done by people against the pandemic in this prolonged? It seems to depend on social behavior change, which starts from the self-reliance of each person to obtain collective awareness in the community. That there is the common enemy, it is COVID-19, it must be dealing by raising body immunity dan vaccination.

Strategy to Recovery and Harmonizing Life with Nature

The strategy ergonomic holistic against pandemics is primarily to find out the root causes, formulate them, and develop a strategic plan to offer alternative solutions against pandemics. Based on an overview of the pandemic. However, it does not mean interrupting programs the government and experts have done. However, to appreciate it. The ergonomic holistic approach emphasizes the impact that occurs. And how nature reacts to sympathetic activity and how the people react to prevent the pandemic. Then what ergonomically activities to promote self-reliance by the one-self to prevent the diseases from spreading and increasing the body’s immunity against the pandemic. Therefore, hopefully, people’s productivity independently synergies with programs of its government and experts sustain progress. It is a sensible alternative to the holistic ergonomics approach and at a small cost (if any).

However, to support the government policies and experts, everyone is consistently applying the health protocol. Furthermore, there are several things that people can do against the pandemic. People should not merely wait for the vaccine to come and do nothing. Suppose every person, family, and community achieve this plan strategically into ergonomic action. Optimistically, with anticipation, it supports the solution of the government and experts in every country.

After observing the surrounding pandemic with people in its problems, it seems that there is no other way unless going back to the basics of life. People should recognize their weaknesses and begin to rebuild strength and personality by self-leadership with self-discovery and self-learning. And one principle that has been adhered to is the body’s immunity against diseases. It would

be delightful if the body's immunity were formed naturally by food and a healthy lifestyle. Therefore, people should return to the basics where they traditionally live using the essential resources of nature. It is back to nature, and people must be capable of living in harmony with nature.

Every ethnic community in the world accepts traditional and interdependent values with nature as part of its culture. Start with the existing, like values of life from what has passed down. People can sort out the traditional values that they obtain. Indeed, not all the patriarchal values have to use today. Some rational and spiritual arguments are accepted and carried out in modern life. Namely: the rituals, traditional medicine (palliative treatment), organic food, and regulating the amount and type of food eaten every day. Enjoy a substantial activity at homes such as gardening, handicrafts, and other beneficial activities; or practicing Yoga. Its activities can intensify stamina and the body's immunity.

Each person must prepare to survive for the worst, training the self-awareness of the potential harm in its environment by understanding the signs of nature. To attaining on how being small-scale farmers that produce the basics need organically. Such as vegetables, tomatoes, chilies, and others by utilizing the remaining space, having fun of this activity as a stress reliever. Thereby are helping mentally and spiritually to increase the body's immunity. It also at least reduces expenses that are using for other needs. Make life changes gradually and consistently. The key represents self-discipline and maintaining a harmonious life with nature. It must conceive those humans have limited power over this universe. In this world, there are many living-being before humans, and humans are a part of the evolution cycle according to the universe's laws. Therefore, people should respect other living-being in nature.

CONCLUSIONS

Everyone never imagines when a tiny living being is named Coronavirus (COVID-19). It has been carried by humans and spread by modern transportation. When there was a pandemic occurred, it is the breakdown of humanity. The world virtually and reality collapsed against the pandemic for more than one year. Everything has been an effort to take it down, and still no signs it goes down. Even in the middle of solutions developing processes, there is an emerging variant of COVID-19; and spread around the world. Prevention of its spread by implementing health protocols and social restrictions. The efforts to increase public immunity by trying synthetic herd immunity around the world. However, many factors need establishing, and it is uneasy and conducts for years. Apart from technical problems, the government and experts have attempted various solutions, but its implementation is a blunder in the people. Indeed, this is not a stand-alone issue; many aspects influence each other. A critical factor that affects people and social behavior, apart from the pandemic, represents the economic decline in the domestic, national, regional, and the world. Undoubtedly, the changes in behavior are unconscious, especially difficulties of the economy, added to the worse pandemic, and everything changes.

After observing many aspects, the result from the analysis of ergonomics holistic is that it depends on each person on the awareness of critical conditions and situations. The solution lies in one's self-reliance. Therefore, this is time for the people to raise their self-leadership, inspiring by Swaraj and Swadeshi, to safety the self, family, and society. One principle that adheres to is the body's immunity against diseases. It would be by food and a healthy lifestyle. For that, people should return to patriarchal values, namely back to nature. Every ethnic community accepts traditional and interdependent natural values of life. And there are many of them, such as the rituals, traditional medicine, organic food, and regulating the amount and type of food eaten every day, enjoying beneficial activities, or practicing Yoga. And more important is maintaining a harmonious life with nature.

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Cite this Article: Tjokorda Bagus Putra Marhaendra, Yeyen Komalasari, I Gusti Bagus Rai Utama (2021). The Ergonomic Holistic Management Strategy against the Covid-19 Pandemic. International Journal of Current Science Research and Review, 4(11), 1555-1562